

SCIENTIFIC ASPECTS OF THE DEVELOPMENT OF PHENOMENON OF RESPONSIBILITY IN ENTREPRENEURS

V.M.Khalimova

Head of the department of pedagogy and psychology, doctor of psychology sciences, professor,
Andijan state pedagogical institute

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8027655>

Abstract. *This article provides information on the responsibility of interpersonal relations in entrepreneurial activity. Today, the issue of responsibility is relevant for all industries. In this article, responsibility for entrepreneurship is seen as a key factor.*

Keywords: *market economy, entrepreneurship, responsibility, instrumental exchanges, social system.*

An entrepreneur foresees opportunities to satisfy a need or desire in the market and, with the intention of satisfying them, attracts the necessary investments, integrates labor force and means of production in the production process. If entrepreneurial activity is interpreted in terms of its goals and tasks, it is first of all embodied as a method that realizes the economic interests of the market economy [1]. In a more precise sense, it is a set of organizational-economic, financial, legal and other economic relations that serve and operate in the reproduction of individual links of the market economy. The property and other assets used in the production process do not fully manifest themselves economically without entrepreneurial activity and, of course, do not bring enough income to the producers of goods. Therefore, entrepreneurship, figuratively speaking, is the blood circulation system of the market economy, which maintains the vital activity of each economic link and “predicts the social exchange of goods”. An entrepreneur is a person who undertakes bold, important and complex goals, takes full responsibility for the implementation of new ideas, and takes risks. Entrepreneurship is the economic activity of its subjects in order to make a profit, taking risks and taking ownership responsibility within the framework of current laws [1]. At the same time, the concept of individuality in interpersonal relations has a wide place in entrepreneurial activities. “Responsibility” is an Arabic word that expresses the concepts of responsibility and accountability. Responsibility for the result of an action, behavior is responsibility. Although we use this word a lot, we usually do not pay attention to its essence, we often do not feel the burden of this word. We know that the root of the word “responsibility” means - responsible. It refers to the concepts of being charged with responsibility, responsible for, responsible for. This concept seems to apply to all of existence. The whole world is governed by the law of responsibility, responsibility, responsibility. The sun is responsible for the day, the moon is responsible for the night, the rain and snow is responsible for the earth, and the earth is responsible for every creature in its bosom.

They balance their responsibilities and always obediently create opportunities. This is the great art of the Creator and the immortal law of nature. A person who understands the essence of his creation, recognizes his creator and lives striving to please him, fully feels and acts on all responsibilities. In the course of his life, a person gradually fulfills responsibilities of different contents and forms: filial responsibility; parental, sisterly, brotherly responsibility; wifehood - family responsibility; kinship, friendship, fraternal responsibility, neighborliness, neighborhood responsibility; studentship, apprenticeship, student responsibility; profession, job, position,

responsibility... In the end, there are various and endless responsibilities in one person's life. It is from this responsibility that duties and tasks are created and fulfilled. If people of different categories and positions, of different ages and circumstances, who are influencing various processes in society, realize their responsibilities and manage to live in their own time, the progress of development, the rise of spirituality, and the development of enlightenment are guaranteed. It is clear from the comments that there is a strong need to take a deep look at the concept of "responsibility", to reform spiritual and educational activities and resources aimed at correcting its executors.

Before considering responsibility as a reciprocal relationship, attention should be paid to domestic and foreign research in this area. Responsibility is, of course, a broad and multifaceted concept. What is of interest to many humanities (philosophy, ethics, law, political science, medicine, psychology, etc.), as a result, contains many meanings, interpretations and is viewed from different angles and does not have a clear definition. starts with The philosophical dictionary includes the following definitions: "responsibility belongs to the moral and legal category, which reflects the specific social and moral-legal attitude of society (humanity in general) characterized by the fulfillment of the moral duty and legal norms of a person." The definition also emphasizes that responsibility is central to the problem of the relationship between human capacities to act as the subject of one's actions. Shows the duration of consideration of the category of responsibility in the category of freedom. In terms of specific issues of responsibility, the individual's ability to consciously fulfill certain requirements is emphasized; perform their duties; making the right spiritual choice; achieve a certain result.

Definitions of economic dictionaries define duty as a duty and a right, and usually include types of liability, such as legal, disciplinary, material, criminal, moral. Thus, this responsibility performs the task of regulating the obligations of the subject of economic relations. The most detailed and comprehensive analysis of the concept of responsibility from the point of view of linguistics is necessary.

An analysis of the concepts of responsibility in the dictionaries of different nations showed that the meaning of the word "responsibility" in Uzbek, Russian, English, German, and French languages is accidental: "... in all languages, responsibility is associated with duty, obligation, and the need to perform". [2]

The psychological understanding of responsibility is also diverse and includes different meanings. Here, authors with different information, different meaning and content from different positions are accepted with responsibility. Such diversity, on the one hand, loses the focus of attention of the researcher, but on the other hand, complexity, multi affectedness, a wide range of functions in the personality structure and the multiplicity of a certain psychological phenomenon are manifested.

From this point of view, we will dwell on the views of Western scientists. The views of L.Coldberg are very popular. The author emphasizes the importance of active creative interaction with the environment as the main factor in the development of human moral consciousness. Five stages of the development of moral consciousness are emphasized in the analysis of the decision by moral subjects that conflict with two types of generally accepted moral standards:

1. "objective responsibility"
2. "subjective responsibility"
3. "instrumental exchange"

4. “social system and ethics of conscience”

5. Understanding the responsibility based on the ethical norms accepted in the society [3].

In addition to understanding the formation of responsibility as a process of active interaction of a person with the environment, it plays an important role in the concept of L.Koldberg, who promotes responsibility that regulates social behavior. K.Helkama studied the process of assuming responsibility. It highlights several developmental stages of taking responsibility:

1. Autonomous subjective responsibility
2. Accountability as a social responsibility
3. Responsibility based on ethical standards

F.Haider formulated the main principles of the concept of the resulting attribute. This direction is widely accepted in foreign psychology and shows subjectivity, which is called the aspect of responsibility. Identification of results (identification of causes) - attempts to explain the causes of certain events that occur everywhere in the daily life of people. Therefore, it is the "man-to-man" responsibility created to analyze the behavior and characteristics of the concept. Based on the three main assumptions here, F.Haider was told that people tend to attribute the cause to an actor (“actor”) or to the environment.

“First, the appropriate behavior of a person’s social actions depends mainly on how he understands and defines the world around him.

Second, people want to predict and control the environment, their environment. This desire arises if one is able to correctly determine the causes of other people's actions, correctly determine the roots of the origin of social events.

Third, there is an analogy between the perception of social and physical objects “. [4]

Therefore, events depend on the ratio of external forces and personality resources. F.Haider emphasizes that it depends on the measure of responsibility, based on the assessment of the individual contribution of each of these two factors. After all, a person can be responsible for the events and consequences that they can influence.

F.Haider defines 5 levels of responsibility sharing:

1. Association - the responsibility of a person for any result related to or related to him.
2. Insight - responsibility for the “origin” by man. If a person is a necessary condition for an event, it is taken into account even if the outcome is not foreseeable.
3. Contingency - the liability depends on any event that may be foreseen even if it is not related to the purposes.
4. Intention - responsibility for what is initiated by a person and what should be done.
5. Authenticity - what is happening is shared with the environment and partially explained to them. [5]

From one to the fifth degree, personal contribution to what is happening, but difficult situations that reduce the level of responsibility of the fifth degree are taken into account. In the formation of relationship responsibility in business activity, all parts of responsibility are of great importance.

REFERENCES

1. Абдуллаев А.,Муфтайдинов Қ, Айбешов Х. Кичик бизнесни бошқариш: Дарслик.- Т .: Молия, 2003.-191б.

2. Джон Берджес, Дон Штайнхофф, Основы управления малым бизнесом. Перевод с англ. - М.: БИНОМ, 1997
3. Кревенс, Дэвид, В.. Стратегический маркетинг, 6-е изд. Пер. с англ. М.: Издательский дом “Вильямс”, 2003.- 752с.
4. Титова О.И. Тендерные особенности отношения российских предпринимателей к конкуренции и партнерству. Дис. ... канд. психол.наук. М., 2007. 167 с.
5. ТугареваЕ.В. Процессы предпочтения и отвержения как основания социального выбора. Дис.... канд. психол. наук. М., 1996. 162 с.